

Gender differences in the job satisfaction among five-star hotel employees : A study of Hyderabad, India

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ABSTRACT

Background : In India there have been few research conducted on the job satisfaction of hotel employees. This study lies on the central paradox of gender and job satisfaction. The main objective of this study is to examine the gender differences in job satisfaction among the hoteliers. **Methods :** A total of 142 hotel employees (62 Females & 80 Males) were taken into consideration for the study. A standardized tool identified as Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) Short form is used to establish the satisfaction levels in different parameters. The questionnaire also comprised of demographic profile of the hotel employees. The data is analysed with the help of SPSS. **Results :** This gender difference is largely explained by female's underrepresentation in hotel industry and having inferior jobs as compared to their male counterparts. Number of male hotel employees is higher in food production department as compared to female hotel employees. Females showed greater overall satisfaction in comparison with males. Significant gender differences were majorly found in remuneration aspect of job satisfaction in comparison with the work load. **Conclusions :** Gender differences in job satisfaction did exist among five- star hotel employees in India. **Keywords :** Gender, job satisfaction, hotel employees, five star hotels, gender equality.

1. Introduction

A substantial research study exists concerning diversity of gender in hospitality industry. Previous researchers establish that soaring job satisfaction is evident by employee loyalty like good citizenship performance (Rusbult et al., 1988). In a gender study, the research focus is on men and women, their attitudes, behavioural qualities, competencies and skilfulness. Gender diversity is just one of the means of making certain that increasing work requirements are rightfully addressed. The researchers (Kreps 1971; Berch 1982; Featherman and Hauser 1976) as well found that women embrace jobs that are, on average, substandard in several respects to those held by men.

Job satisfaction is defined as optimistic feelings about one's job based on one's appraisal of the features of the job (Robbins & Judge, 2007).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is defined as a set of feelings and beliefs that a person has about his job (George & Jones, 1999) or as an optimistic emotional state that result from the assessment of the occurrences given by the job (Locke, 1976). Job satisfaction is an important facet of any organization to retain its employees. (Spector, 1997) concised job satisfaction determinants such as communication, approval, co-workers, job conditions, tassel benefits, the nature of the organization itself, environment of the work itself, an organization's policies and measures, personal growth, endorsement opportunities, salary, recognition, security and management. (Ghiselli et al., 2001) study opines that employees who are not satisfied with their job are more likely to leave their place than those who are satisfied

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with their job. Job satisfaction is a sign of physiological and mental health in addition to emotions of the personnel.

2.2 Gender & Job Satisfaction

Men are dominant, women are submissive;” “Men are aggressive, women are passive;” “Men are agentic, women are communal;” “Men are power-centric, women are person-centric;” “Men are single-focused, women are multi-focused;” “Men are bread winners, women are home makers.” The record of differences recognized by researchers is faultless (Asha Kaul, 2009). (Al-Ajmi, 2006) The findings concerning gender differences linked to job satisfaction have been not in agreement from the 1950s to date. For example, some studies (e.g. Ferrer-iCarbonell and Mora, 2009) suggested that males demonstrate more satisfaction in their job than females. Yet, other studies specify that females have more satisfaction than males (Okpara et al., 2005; Clark, 1996; Kim, 2005; Jung et al., 2007). Bilgic (1998) did not find clear gender differences in overall job satisfaction in Turkey, but did indicate apparent and significant gender differences related to pay satisfaction and satisfaction with the physical environment. Job satisfaction is same for women and men, they behave differently in working environments and because of it their satisfaction varies (Marco, D., 2014).

The relationship between job satisfaction and gender differences has been examined quite a few times, with differing results. A number of studies have indicated women to be more satisfied than men (Clark, 1996, 1997; Sloane & Williams, 1996; Ishitani, 2010), while others have revealed men to be more satisfied than women (Aydin, Uysal, & Sarier, 2012; Mora & Ferrer-iCarbonell, 2009; Kim, Murrmann, & Lee, 2009).

According to Malka and Chatman (2003) job orientation symbolizes work-related choices to value specific categories of rewards innate in the work environment. The research of De Vaus and McAllister (1991) depicts gender differences in view to what women and men consider in a job. A number of other studies, such as Loscocco (1989), demonstrate that women value extrinsic job characteristics more than men do. However, there are other researches that illustrate the opposite (Neil

& Snizek, 1987). Finally, certain researchers have found no differences in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic job orientation between men and women (Brief, Rose, & Aldag, 1977). Some researchers observe gender differences in service orientation and job satisfaction, by means of closely comparable data collected in nine Western European countries (De Vaus & McAllister, 1991). Their results display that men are fairly more satisfied than women with their jobs and place superior value than women on both extrinsic and intrinsic work principles.

2.3 Women at work in Hotels: A brief look at Gender Equality

Women as managers are more innovative, good at synchronizing activities, prioritize work and more involved in mentoring programs. Caruso, Mayer, and Salovey (2002) highlighted that women have an immense capability to recognize other people's emotions and are closer in communication with others. Campos-Soria, Marchante-Mera, & Ropero-García (2011) research examines that women are employed at all levels of the organisational structure, including management, and this conveys transformations in the universal outset of the hotel business. There is a study that demonstrates women at the workplace are better at controlling emotions of stress (Kruml & Geddes, 2000). Female workforce cannot move from one place to another and cannot work for long hours in the organization (Pinar et al., 2011). Females who are extremely qualified, cannot attain administrative rank in the organizations (Li and Leung, 2001). Several studies accomplished by researchers (Biswas and Cassell, 1996; Purcell 1996; Sparrowe and Iverson, 1999) exhibit a dissimilar distribution of earnings between female and male workforce in the hospitality industry, with females earning a lesser amount than their male counterparts.

3. Theoretical Framework of the Present Study

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of the present study

Source: Author's Compilation

The theoretical framework is drawn after extensive review of existing literature. This framework depicts the effect of gender on job satisfaction with the help of demographic variables and work-related variables.

The present study is designed to test the following Hypotheses:

H1: There would be a gender difference in job satisfaction among the five star hotel employees.

H2: Gender would contribute to describe job satisfaction in hotels.

H3: Women would emphasize on intrinsic factors of job satisfaction and men would emphasize on extrinsic factors of job satisfaction.

4. Research Methodology

4.1. Sample

To examine the effects of gender on job satisfaction of five star hotel workforces, a questionnaire survey was performed. The population of the study consists of the five star hotel employees of Hyderabad, India (N=150). All the hoteliers were sent a questionnaire, a total of 142 questionnaires (62 females and 80 males) were received with usable responses. Table I details the demographic profile of the respondents. The table represents the number and percentage of sample under the following categories: gender, age, marital status, job position, work department, academic profile, and total experience in hotels and in current hotel, nature of employment, monthly income and gender of immediate boss.

Table I: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable(N=142)			
		N	(%)
Gender	Male	80	56.3
	Female	62	43.7
Age(years)	21-25	44	31.0
	26-30	26	18.3
	31-35	32	22.5
	36-40	23	16.2
	>40	17	12.0
Marital Status	Married	70	49.3
	Unmarried	72	50.7
Job Position	Managerial	84	59.2
	Operational	38	26.8
	Supervisory	20	14.1
Department	Food & Beverage Service	21	14.8

	Food Production	14	9.9
	Front Office	44	31.0
	House Keeping	20	14.1
	Others	43	30.3
Academic Profile	Diploma	6	4.2
	Graduate	99	69.7
	Post Graduate	37	26.1
Total Experience in Previous Hotel	<1 years	15	10.6
	1-5 years	31	21.8
	>5 years	96	67.6
Total Experience in Current Hotel	<1 years	37	26.1
	1-5 years	93	65.5
	>5 years	12	8.5
Nature of Employment	Permanent	37	26.1
	Contractual	93	65.5
	Temporary	12	8.5
Monthly Income	<20,000	17	12.0
	20,000-30,000	26	18.3
	30,000-40,000	54	38.0
	>40,000	45	31.7
Immediate Boss	Male	127	89.4
	Female	15	10.6

Source: Author's Compilation of primary data

Table II: P-value and gender based percentage of demographics

Variable(N=142)		Gender		<i>p-value</i>
		Male(N=80)	Female(N=62)	
		N (%)	N (%)	
Age(years)	21-25	17(21.3%)	27(43.5%)	0.033*
	26-30	15(18.8%)	11(17.7%)	
	31-35	23(28.7%)	9(14.5%)	
	36-40	16(20.0%)	7(11.3%)	
	>40	9(11.3%)	8(12.9%)	
Marital Status	Married	44(55.0%)	26(41.9%)	0.122
	Unmarried	36(45.0%)	36(58.1%)	
Job Position	Managerial	58(72.5%)	26(41.9%)	<0.001*
	Operational	12(15.0%)	26(41.9%)	
	Supervisory	10(12.5%)	10(16.1%)	
Department	Food & Beverage Service	11(13.8%)	10(16.1%)	0.084
	Food Production	12(15.0%)	2(3.2%)	
	Front Office	20(25.0%)	24(38.7%)	
	House Keeping	10(12.5%)	10(16.21%)	
	Others	27(33.8%)	16(25.8%)	
Academic Profile	Diploma	4(5.0%)	2(3.2%)	0.866
	Graduate	55(68.8%)	44(71.0%)	
	Post Graduate	21(26.3%)	16(25.8%)	
Total Experience in Previous Hotel	<1 years	10(12.5%)	5(8.1%)	<0.001
	1-5 years	7(8.8%)	24(38.7%)	

	>5 years	6(7.5%)	6(9.7%)	
Nature of Employment	Permanent	17(21.3%)	20(32.3%)	0.253
	Contractual	57(71.3%)	36(58.1%)	
	Temporary	6(7.5%)	6(9.7%)	
Monthly Income	<20,000	7(8.8%)	10(16.1%)	0.169
	20,000-30,000	12(15.0%)	14(22.6%)	
	30,000-40,000	36(45.0%)	18(29.0%)	
	>40,000	25(31.3%)	20(32.3%)	
Immediate Boss	Male	73(91.3%)	54(87.1%)	0.425
	Female	7(8.8%)	8(12.9%)	

Source: Author's Compilation of primary data

Table II determines the p-value of the demographic variables. Job position (p-value = <0.001) and total experience in previous hotels (p-value= <0.001) were found to be significant. While other demographic factors such as age (p-value= 0.033), marital status (p value = 0.122), department (p-value= 0.084), academic profile (p-value = 0.866), total experience in current hotel (p-value = 0.253), nature of employment (p-value=0.253), monthly income (p-value=0.169) and immediate boss (p-value= 0.425) were established to be non-significant.

4.2. Measures

The Short-form of Minnesota satisfaction

Questionnaire (MSQ) was used in the study. The Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) assesses 20 aspects of job satisfaction: Ability utilization, social service, achievement, advancement, authority, creativity, company policies & practices, compensation, activity, co-workers, independence, moral values, recognition, responsibility, job security, supervision (Technical), supervision (Human Relations), social status, variety and working conditions. The respondents were asked to respond to the above items on a 5-point scale; 5 represents very satisfied, 4 represents satisfied, 3 represents neutral, 2 represents dissatisfied and 1 represents very dissatisfied.

Table III: Extrinsic and Intrinsic Job satisfaction factors

Extrinsic Factors	Intrinsic Factors
Compensation	Achievement
Job Security	Independence
Authority	Moral values
Advancement	Responsibility
Company policies & Practices	Social Service
Creativity	Co-workers
Recognition	Supervision (Human Relations)
Social Status	Activity
Working Conditions	Ability Utilization
Variety	Supervision (Technical)

Source: Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ)

4.3. Statistical Methods

To establish whether there was a significant difference in job satisfaction between male and female hotel employees mean comparisons were used. Male and female employees were also evaluated with respect to the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) 20 aspects of job satisfaction.

4.4. Results

The next question to be discovered was that the gender contributes to the difference in job satisfaction. I have compared the gender differences in the importance of each job aspect to answer the above question (after controlling the other demographic variables). There was no significant relationship found between gender and intrinsic and extrinsic factors of job satisfaction.

Table IV is a summary of the responses, which is used to evaluate the gender differences in job satisfaction. Table IV represents the mean scores and p-value. The

above data represents that the male employees are less satisfied (both extrinsic and intrinsic factors) whereas female employees were found to be more satisfied (both extrinsic and intrinsic factors). Male employees not satisfied with the intrinsic factors were found to be 35(43.7%) and male employees satisfied with the intrinsic factors were found to be 45(56.3%). Female employees not satisfied with the intrinsic factors were found to be 26(41.9%) and female employees satisfied with the intrinsic factors were found to be 36(58.1%) and the consolidated p-value is 0.828. Male employees not satisfied with the extrinsic factors were found to be 36(45.0%) and male employees satisfied with the extrinsic factors were found to be 44(55.0%). Female employees not satisfied with the extrinsic factors were found to be 25(40.3%) and female employees satisfied with the extrinsic factors were found to be 37(59.7%) and the consolidated p-value is 0.577.

Table IV: Job satisfaction on the basis of gender and p-value

	Male	Female	p-value
Intrinsic Factor			
Not Satisfied	35(43.7%)	26(41.9%)	0.828
Satisfied	45(56.3%)	36(58.1%)	
Extrinsic Factor			
Not Satisfied	36(45.0%)	25(40.3%)	0.577
Satisfied	44(55.0%)	37(59.7%)	

Source: Author's Compilation of primary data

We summarize the results as women are more satisfied than men.

6. Conclusion

The present research has quite a few practical and managerial implications. The hotel managers can formulate strategies to retain employees and boost their satisfaction in the job. Men value extrinsic factors such as promotion/ advancement more whereas women value intrinsic factors more. The results support the hypothesis that women and men may vary in terms of work

orientation.

Thus it is better to explain the gender differences in job satisfaction with the value-percept theory (Locke,1976)—that the significant job facets for women are dissimilar from those for men, and the discrepancies between what is desired and received in the significant job facets for men are greater than those in the important job aspects for women.

This study is exploratory. Thus further research can be conducted to confirm the findings.

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